

Advancing benthic monitoring for marine biodiversity policy implementation

To support the effective implementation of the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), the Water Framework Directive (WFD), the Habitats Directive, the Nature Restoration Regulation (NRR), and the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, **OBAMA-NEXT scientists recommend policymakers at EU and Member State levels to consider the following recommendations:**

- Advance standardisation of monitoring tools and workflows.
- Strengthen integration of emerging technologies into operational monitoring to expand the scale and increasing accuracy and speed of assessments.
- Improve assessments of habitat condition and ecosystem function to support policy implementation.
- Build capacity for long-term, scalable implementation of new technologies.

Benthic biodiversity – organisms living on or in the seafloor – **and the habitats they form support essential ecosystem functions** such as nutrient cycling, carbon storage, and structural habitat for marine life. European environmental directives, including the MSFD, Habitats Directive, and the NRR, explicitly reference benthic components, as these are critical to achieving EU Biodiversity Strategy and the EU's climate goals as set out in The EU Green Deal.

However, the current state of benthic biodiversity monitoring remains inadequate to meet these policies' requirements.

- There are **critical data** gaps in species distribution and spatial coverage, particularly for structurally complex or sensitive habitats.
- Habitat condition** is often **poorly defined and inconsistently assessed** among regions, undermining restoration planning, goals, and accountings, as well as providing sound scientific support for the design of ecologically coherent networks of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs).
- Monitoring approaches remain fragmented** and poorly harmonized across Member States, affecting data comparability and coordinated reporting under EU and regional frameworks.

Relevance of benthic monitoring tools for policy implementation

Benthic monitoring tools provide spatially explicit, ecologically meaningful, and legally relevant information that is critical to implement EU marine policies.

- **Habitat maps and seafloor integrity indicators** generated from remote sensing and modelling approaches directly support assessments under MSFD Descriptor 1 (Biodiversity) and Descriptor 6 (Seafloor integrity), member state reporting on the implementation and effectiveness of conservation measures (Article 17 of the Habitats Directive), as well as the attainment of the marine restoration targets established in Article 5 of the Nature Restoration Regulation (Annex II Habitats). Such indicators **can help identifying priority areas for conservation and restoration** based on habitat distribution and condition.
- **eDNA and trait-based indicators** enhance biodiversity monitoring under MSFD Descriptor 1, Descriptor 5 (Eutrophication), and can inform on ecosystem function and food web structure relevant to Descriptor 4 (Food webs). These tools are particularly useful for characterising carbon-rich benthic ecosystems and **supporting the ecological restoration targets** of the NRR.
- **Remote sensing and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs)** can enable the tracking of restoration success and habitat recovery in shallow coastal areas, contributing to MPA management and effectiveness assessments in line with the EU's commitment to improving coverage and effectiveness of MPAs as set out in the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and member states' obligations under the Habitats Directive.
- **Integrated, long-term datasets** that combine environmental pressures with biodiversity responses **support the evaluation of cumulative impacts** and are essential for **informing adaptive management strategies** under both EU and regional marine frameworks and quality monitoring required of member states under the EU legislative instruments addressing marine biodiversity.

OBAMA-NEXT contributions to policy-relevant data needs

To support the realisation of key obligations and commitments for marine biodiversity in EU policy instruments, OBAMA-NEXT has developed and tested a **series of Information Products (IP) to address key data needs and gaps** limiting the effective implementation of various EU biodiversity and marine environmental policies. These contributions demonstrate how advanced tools and integrated workflows can **improve the monitoring of benthic habitats** and biodiversity in support of the MSFD, Habitats Directive, and the NRR.

■ The IP on **coastal vegetation mapping using remote sensing** applied machine learning to integrate drone imagery and satellite data, generating high-resolution maps of benthic habitats, such as seagrass and macroalgae. This approach enabled the **upscaling of local habitat observations to support consistent and repeatable mapping** across EU regions. In particular, a coherent mapping study executed in several OBAMA-NEXT learning sites demonstrated how these methods can be applied uniformly across different regions, **improving the comparability and spatial coverage of benthic habitat types**. This directly addresses long-standing challenges in habitat classification consistency and spatial data gaps, supporting reporting requirements under the MSFD (Descriptor 6), Habitats Directive, and the Nature Restoration Regulation.

■ The IP on **comparison of remote sensing and habitat distribution models** further provides an in-depth comparison of the advantages and disadvantages of remote sensing and species distribution model-based approaches for coastal habitat mapping, thus **providing practical guidance on the use of these key methodological tools**. For instance, remote sensing can only be used in relatively shallow areas, whereas predictive approaches help fill spatial gaps in monitoring data, especially in deeper areas and places that are logistically difficult or costly to survey.

This is the first step towards **employing multiple methodologies to support coherent habitat mapping at the scale required for effective policy implementation**.

■ The IP on **mapping of biomass and carbon content of coastal vegetation using green LiDAR on drones** produced centimeter-scale 3D models of key habitats, such as seagrass meadows and other vegetated habitats. Combined with the other remotely sensed map products previously highlighted, these outputs provide detailed information on the volume (i.e., biomass), structure, and in some cases habitat condition, which are **critical for assessing degradation levels and guiding restoration priorities**. By enabling spatially explicit and repeatable assessments of condition, this product addresses a major challenge in implementing the Nature Restoration Regulation, where restoration efforts must target areas that are 'not in good condition' but where suitable data are currently lacking.

■ The IP on the **position paper on eDNA** use for stakeholders **consolidates expert consensus** across five Horizon Europe projects (OBAMA-NEXT, BIOcean5D, MARCO-BOLO, MARBEFES). It **defines which eDNA methods are most suitable for different marine monitoring needs** and offers harmonized guidance for integrating eDNA into regulatory frameworks, helping to address the lack of standard protocols and recognized applications for different taxonomical levels.

Recommendations

Advance standardisation of monitoring tools and workflows

- Promote the coherent application of remote sensing methods to support EU-wide consistency in habitat classification.
- Integrate the use of eDNA tools to inform the development of standardized protocols for eDNA-based assessments, enabling regulatory uptake across Member States.
- Align indicator development and monitoring outputs with Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) and Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) frameworks. For example, ecosystem distribution and condition of seagrass habitats that have been monitored in several OBAMA-NEXT IPs are relevant to EU Biodiversity Observation Coordination Centre pilot indicators.

Strengthen integration of emerging technologies into operational monitoring

- Facilitate the adoption of remote sensing, such as satellites and drones, equipped with different types of sensors, by incorporating the workflows tested in OBAMA-NEXT into national monitoring schemes under the MSFD and the Nature Restoration Regulation.
- Support the development of interoperable, multi-tool monitoring designs, such as making remote sensing and species distribution models interchangeable in a compatible way, to enhance spatial data coverage and methodological complementarity.

Improve assessments of habitat condition and ecosystem function

- Apply high-resolution spatial tools, such as drone-based mapping, to monitor the structural complexity, biomass, and degradation status of vegetated habitats, supporting restoration planning under the NRR.
- Advance the use of eDNA approaches to capture biodiversity patterns, ecosystem function, and environmental status assessments.

Build capacity for long-term, scalable implementation

- Invest in the replication and transferability of OBAMA-NEXT products across additional regions and habitat types, ensuring that workflows remain scalable and policy-relevant.
- Facilitate training, inter-agency coordination, and technical guidance to embed new tools in routine monitoring practices, drawing from OBAMA-NEXT demonstration activities and stakeholder engagement outputs.

Authors

Leal, M.C., Forsblom, L., Ojaveer, H., Borja, A., Papadopoulou, N., Outhwaite, O., Walton, R., Carstensen, J., Gundersen, H.

References and resources

Deliverable 3.1. Review of existing and emerging techniques for benthic habitats
(<https://zenodo.org/records/14099051>)

Deliverable 6.1. Review, analysis and crosswalk of the data requirements of key policies
(<https://zenodo.org/records/13981477>)

OBAMA-NEXT information products (<https://obama-next.eu/information-products/>)

 As this policy brief is a deliverable of the project, minor changes can be made during 2026 after the project review meeting.

For additional resources from OBAMA-NEXT project, visit the web page:
<https://obama-next.eu>

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